

Breaking the Shackles of Tradition; A Study of Manju Kapur's *Difficult Daughters*, *A Married Woman and Home*

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Manju Kapur's novels attempt the exixtential problems faced by the educated Indian woman with genuiness and insight. They fight between tradition and modernity. They become strong in their sufferings, and they constantly fight back to exist, to free themselves from the shackles of tradition and other prejudices. Difficult Daughters by Manju Kapur tells how virmati is torn between her family duties, the desire of education and illicit love. In A Married Woman, the life of Astha as depicted by Manju kapur reveals her earnest quest for equality, for considering her an equal being and a worthy member of the society. Manju kapur's Home also explores Nisha as a new woman appears before us more assertive, self-secured and confident one. By equally footing with man, she proclaims her womanhood in a bold manner. Manju Kapur deals with excess of marital problems that attack the educated working middle class wives of India.

Keywords: Freedom, self-realization, suffering, equality, identity, family, marriage.

Manju Kapur has offered a new protagonist in her novels whom we can call a new woman. In all her novels, she has come with a new woman with more dignity and determination. Her protagonists are very bold that they can give up anything for their own identity and this was a new tendency which emerged in the novels of Manju Kapur.

The women in her novels seem to be the epitome of new women who have been carrying the burden of inhibition since ages and want to break that tradition of silence now. In the traditional social background of her novels, she shows the survival of mothers and daughters. In the same society where marriage is considered as the ultimate goal and destiny from which these women have no way out. Manju Kapur's female protagonists from Virmati to Nina are the representatives of that female folk who yearn to be free from the rotten social customs and traditions but are never allowed. Her

female protagonists are mostly educated. Their education leads them to independent thinking, for which their family and society become intolerant towards them. They fight between tradition and modernity. It is their individual struggle with family and society through which they thrust into a dedicated effort to shape an identity for themselves as qualified women with flawless backgrounds.

Her novels attempt the existential problems faced by the educated Indian woman with genuineness and insight. These novels depict the fight against taboos, social limitations and manmade code of conduct in a traditional society and insight. Her heroines from Virmati to Nina are the pictogram of female imagination responding to pressures and oppressions of patriarchal culture where marriage is seen only as a compromise. Her novels are a story of struggle for self-determination and search for an existence at various levels. She tries to bring out significant new meanings in the changed paradigm of cultural encounters in which conjugal roles, dual burdens, equal opportunities and social constraints are seen from the existential point of view. The protagonists of her novels try to maintain stability all the time. They become strong in their sufferings amidst the dual standards and they constantly fight back to exist, to free themselves from the shackles of tradition and other prejudices.

In short Manju Kapur has portrayed a mature understanding of the female consciousness and the inner delicacy of a woman's mind. She has been highly bothered by the suffering and meaningless living of the female folk in the patriarchal society, but the stoic woman in her novels constantly tries to set her female protagonists free from the meaningless existence hence we find them constantly struggling against the odds of social and familial system.

Difficult Daughters by Manju Kapur is a fascinating story of a woman torn between contradictory forces of society and her keen desire to break that silence. Though she does her best to break that stillness and to raise arms against social customs and norms but social norms are malicious enough to allow her not to succeed. The story tells how she is torn between her family duties, the desire for education and illicit love. Although Virmati succeeds in breaking all manmade limitations, there are certain polarities so deeply implanted within her that she struggles to shake through the chains. She grows up from a native girl to a woman matured by suffering and through experience. Throughout the novel she is found in the pursuit for true love, quest for freedom, search for the realization of the self... the thirst does not stop. She fights and fights to get what she wants, but in the process of struggle to express herself, she loses an important part of herself and realizes triviality of things.

The term Difficult Daughter refers to Virmati, who is the daughter of prosperous merchant family of Lala Diwan Chand. In the generation of Kasturi, it was branded that woman's role was to child-bearing and kitchen work, but in the generation of Virmati, she took bold and radical steps in joining the political movement for India's freedom, insisted the importance of women education and independence. As we have quoted elsewhere, "as a nonchalant representative of the middle generation, Virmati breaks away from the tradition-bound limits of Indian women. We see a woman, who fights, but falters and fails"(56). Virmati's character is the destiny of a typical Indian woman. We cannot devalue Virmati's struggle just because she failed, but through her courageous attempt, she breaks the patriarchal mould in the forties.

Kapur's obsession with the female revolt against age old customs, traditions, one sided family values and the institution of marriage is followed through her second novel A Married Woman. It is the story of love set against the backdrop of the consequences of the demolition of the Babri Masjid. Astha the protagonist is a typical middle class woman brought up in Delhi. She agrees to an arranged marriage and initially exults in passionate sexuality with the bounds of marriage. Though she appears to be quite happy being a teacher and a mother of two kids, there is always a stream of bitterness against being treated as one of the inferior sex. Hemant, her

husband, shares the burden of looking after their first born and is quite broad-minded in his views. Gradually the outer sheen wears off and Hemant proves to be an autocratic husband. Astha objects and pleads, "Surely, equals could relate better than master and slave". (A Married Woman : 76) she again and again feels her nowhere existence. Her voice of protest and rebellion ultimately results in broadening of silences and the two gradually drift apart. Towards the end we see the silently suffering woman ultimately becomes strong enough to go with Pipeelika on a tour of the country to create an awakening and awareness.

The life of Astha as depicted by Manju Kapur reveals her earnest quest for equality, for considering her an equal being and a worthy member of the society. When she learns that the books had been donated to a library, she quarrelled with Hemant and shouted at her mother.

She feels crushed as she was not consulted before taking any minor and major decisions. One more instance is when Astha's mother sells her plot and gives the balance to Hemant to manage. It is again found that this type of behaviour treating women as weak and inferior aggravates her. It is not that Astha wants to take the position of a man. She accepts her duties at home besides she wants to be a partner in sharing all the accomplishments and managements. This aspiration makes her a new woman who wants to break the tradition of silence among women.

Manju Kapur through the medium of the character of Astha seeks for a space in the life of the women folk. She also demands the position which is equal to man in a society. Astha represents the woman who asks for a bit more of life than tradition. Astha is, thus a new woman who instead of security, comfort and respectability wants her emotions and spiritual needs to be recognized.

Manju Kapur's *Home* also explores the complex environment of the Indian family and reveals many issues that are deep rooted within the family viz. Revolt against the old traditions, struggle for survival, quest for identity and of course woman's never ending struggle to survive and to break the silence against her own suppression. Nisha, the protagonist of the novel, in the due course of her struggles for identity and survival refuses to reconcile with the patriarchal and male governed society. Nisha as a new woman appears before us more assertive, self – secured, and confident one. By equally footing with man, she proclaims her womanhood in a bold manner.

Nisha, the protagonist, does not accept the traditions as they are, She wants a separate room for herself in home and society. She, as an educated and strong-willed new woman, decides to refuse to be treated as an object instead she tried to establish her own identity. She does not want to wrap her entire life into home; like her brothers she wants to work in shop. She requests her father Yashpal; If only you could take with you, Papaji," She pleaded in a rush, "I have seen girls working in shops. Why should it be only Ajay, Vijay and Raju? There must be something I too can do." (*Home*:2006:268).

This behaviour of Nisha reveals her inner quest for independent survival. It also seeks for equality of sex. This does not stop here even at the time of her marriage, she places condition to her groom that she should have the freedom to run her business even after their marriage. As a business woman, Nisha worked for last two years. It brings to her sense of achievement in life helping her to create her own uniqueness, her own voice, and her own place in the society and in home.

It is necessary to note that she belongs to a middle class family in the metropolitan area and she is born and brought up in India, Where social and cultural scenario is different from that of western countries. Her quest for self identity, struggle for economic independent existence, and her equality with men depend upon Indian social ethos. Manju Kapur, through the character of Nisha, expresses her passionate desire to provide complete liberation to her female characters in Indian socio-cultural scenario. As she herself studied for a few years in the early 1970's, she maintains the character of Nisha to create awareness of women's liberation and equality along with men.

She, through her novels, takes a deep and satisfying look at the sense of displacement often felt by women in the traditional institution of marriage. Manju Kapur deals with the excess of marital problems that attack the educated working middle class wives of India. The displacement that they suffer and their suffocation in the traditional limits of marriage, family and society as a whole is clearly brought out by the novelist in her novels.

The novels of Manju Kapur show that the women of India have achieved success after sixty years of independence, yet there is still a lot to be done. She has to pull herself out of her existential stupor and bring out her essential self by breaking the age old silence of suffering. She should raise her voice against the mental torture that she has undergone down the ages by creating a separate identity and space for herself.

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